

Spectrophotometric Study of VO (II) Complex of Quinizarin-2-Sulphonic Acid

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In continuation of our work on complexes of quinizarin-2-sulphonic acid (abbreviated as QSA) with Fe (III)¹ and UO₂ (II)² ions, it is observed that VO (II) ion with QSA forms a water soluble, pinkish violet complex, in the ratio 1 : 1 at pH 5.0.

QSA used was of B.D.H. chemically pure and VOSO₄.2H₂O of B.D.H. 'Analar' quality. For buffer solutions, electrolyte solutions, instruments and chemicals, the experimental setup and the procedure are the same as in our previous communications^{1,2}. The pH is adjusted by buffering 10 ml. of the mixed solutions with 2 ml. of the required buffer.

Application of the method of Vosburgh and Cooper³ to the system VOSO₄-QSA (in the ratio 4 : 1, 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 4) VO²⁺ to QSA keeping total volume 12 ml. and pH 5.0 demonstrates the formation of only one complex having λ_{\max} . at 480 m μ whereas QSA has its λ_{\max} . at 470 m μ . Since the absorbance of QSA is less than that of the mixture only after 540 m μ , so 550 m μ , 560 m μ and 570 m μ are selected for our study.

Application of Job's method of continued variations⁴ to the system VOSO₄-QSA, keeping the total volume 12 ml. (10 ml. VOSO₄+QSA and 2 ml. of the required buffer) shows that 1 : 1 complex is stable between pH 3.09 to 5.0.

Absorbance is also measured at the chosen wave lengths of a number of solutions containing VOSO₄ and QSA (1 : 1) and adjusted to different pH values by means of suitable buffers. The absorbance of the complex increases upto pH 4.58 and then it decreases. So, all measurements are made at constant pH 5.0.

The 1 : 1 ratio of the complex has been established spectrophotometrically using Job's method⁴ of continued variations, mole-ratio method⁵ and slope ratio method⁶. Molecular extinction, ϵ , comes to 16.5×10^3 at 550 m μ , 10.9×10^3 at 560 m μ and 8.0×10^3 at 570 m μ and pH 5.0 by slope ratio method⁶.

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